

Flow through Porous Medium. Part IV : Permeability of Water and Solutions of Potassium Nitrate, Ammonium Nitrate and Sodium Nitrate through the Natural Oak Wood Membrane

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Permeability coefficients, L_p , for water and aqueous solutions of potassium nitrate, ammonium nitrate and sodium nitrate at different concentrations and at 35° were determined for a natural oak wood membrane of known thickness. It was found that permeability of water was greater than that of ammonium nitrate and sodium nitrate solutions for the concentrations 0.01-0.10 M . However, in the case of 0.01, 0.02 M potassium nitrate solutions the permeability is more than that of water. It has been found that the permeability for any of the above three salts decreases with an increase of concentration. It is attributed to an increase of friction of solute with membrane with the concentration. The frictional coefficients between membrane matrix and water, membrane matrix and solute particles have also been reported. The reflection coefficients for the wood membrane for potassium nitrate, ammonium and sodium nitrate have been estimated and found to be zero.

THE literature on the transport phenomena such as permeation, osmosis etc. in both natural and artificial membrane is voluminous¹ and the studies involve a number of disciplines in science and technology. Some studies on permeability of water, non-electrolyte² and electrolyte³ solutions from a view point of knowing the structure of wood membrane, preservation of wood and testing the applicability of the theory of thermodynamics of irreversible processes⁴ have been reported recently.

In the present investigation, we have selected oak wood (*Quercus incana*) membrane on account of its structure involving straight capillaries⁵ and investigated the flow of different liquids from the view point of the theory of thermodynamics of irreversible processes and in terms of the frictional coefficients of water-membrane and solute-membrane interactions.

Experimental

The experimental apparatus consisted of two chambers separated by the membrane to be studied. A capillary tube was sealed into the smaller of the chambers. Changes in the volume of fluid in this chamber could be determined upto 0.48 microlitre by observing the level of the fluid in the capillary tube through a cathetometer.

Wood piece of known thickness (0.725 cm) and diameter (2.94 cm) was taken from the Hills in Himachal Pradesh at 7000 ft above mean sea level. The membrane, before being fixed in the apparatus with araldite, was thoroughly washed with conductivity water (10^{-8} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹) by forcing water under vacuum. Potassium nitrate and ammonium

nitrate were of G. R. grade and used as such without further purification, whereas sodium nitrate was purified as described elsewhere⁶.

Results and Discussion

The dissipation function⁴, ϕ , for the transport process of liquids through a membrane under the influence of pressure difference and concentration difference can be written as :

$$\phi = J_V \Delta P + J_D \Delta \pi \quad \dots (1)$$

where J_V is the volume flow, J_D is the diffusional flow, ΔP is the difference in hydrostatic pressure and $\Delta \pi$ is the difference in osmotic pressure across the membrane.

The phenomenological equations relating to the flows and forces given in equation (1) are :

$$J_V = L_P \Delta P + L_{P_d} RT \Delta C \quad \dots (2)$$

$$J_D = L_{dP} \Delta P + L_d RT \Delta C \quad \dots (3)$$

where $\Delta \pi = RT \Delta C$. For this system, the Onsager reciprocal relation⁷ is

$$L_{P_d} = L_{dP}$$

where L_P and L_d are the mechanical coefficients of filtration and diffusion respectively.

Let us consider the experiment in which the concentration of the solute is the same on both sides of the membrane, so that $\Delta \pi = 0$. If a pressure difference is maintained across the membrane there exists a volume flow J_V . The values of volume flow, J_V of water and those of potassium nitrate, ammonium nitrate and sodium nitrate solutions at different pressure difference are given in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

TABLE 1—PERMEABILITY DATA FOR WATER THROUGH OAK WOOD MEMBRANE AT DIFFERENT PRESSURES AND AT 35°

ΔP (cm of liquid level)	$J_v \times 10^4$ ($\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{sec}^{-1}$)
5	2.50
10	4.90
15	7.20
20	9.90
25	12.50

TABLE 2—PERMEABILITY DATA FOR DIFFERENT ELECTROLYTE SOLUTIONS AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS AND AT 35°

$\Delta P(\text{cm})$ (Difference in height of the liquid level across the wood membrane)	$J_v \times 10^4 (\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{sec}^{-1})$					
	0.01M	0.02M	0.04M	0.06M	0.08M	0.10M
<i>Potassium Nitrate</i>						
5	3.50	3.87	2.28	1.86	1.76	1.68
10	6.90	5.62	4.11	8.62	3.31	3.02
15	9.20	8.60	6.38	5.27	5.00	4.52
20	13.20	11.79	9.22	6.80	6.38	6.06
25	16.80	14.90	11.66	8.77	8.23	7.64
<i>Ammonium Nitrate</i>						
5	1.00	0.98	0.95	0.92	0.78	0.75
10	2.10	1.92	1.84	1.65	1.64	1.61
15	3.10	2.85	2.76	2.65	2.46	2.41
20	4.00	3.90	3.68	3.58	3.22	3.18
25	5.10	4.87	4.85	4.51	4.01	3.90
<i>Sodium Nitrate</i>						
5	0.77	0.74	0.73	0.72	0.69	0.67
10	1.47	1.42	1.39	1.35	1.34	1.31
15	2.11	2.01	2.00	1.96	1.96	1.89
20	2.75	2.75	2.74	2.71	2.58	2.46
25	3.89	3.85	3.31	3.26	3.14	3.02

When the concentration of the solute is the same on both the sides of the membrane the volume flow, J_v , can be given as :

$$J_v = L_P \Delta P \quad \dots (4)$$

where L_P is the permeability coefficient the values of which are estimated from the plots between J_v and ΔP for water and solutions of KNO_3 , NH_4NO_3 and NaNO_3 at different concentrations. The values of L_P for water, KNO_3 , NH_4NO_3 and NaNO_3 are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3—MECHANICAL FILTRATION COEFFICIENT, L_P , OF THE NATURAL OAK WOOD MEMBRANE FOR WATER AND DIFFERENT SALT SOLUTIONS AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS AND AT 35°

Concentration $C(\text{Mol. l}^{-1})$	$L_P \times 10^9$ ($\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{sec}^{-1} \cdot \text{dyn}^{-1}$)		
	KNO_3	NH_4NO_3	NaNO_3
0 (water)		7.45	
0.01	10.08	3.08	2.16
0.02	9.05	2.92	2.10
0.04	6.70	2.83	2.07
0.06	5.37	2.69	2.04
0.08	5.02	2.43	1.99
0.10	4.68	2.38	1.92

The equation (4) suggests that a linear relation should exist between J_v and ΔP for water and all the solutions of KNO_3 , NH_4NO_3 and NaNO_3 . This has been found to be so. The linear plots further suggest that the Poiseuille's law of flow of liquids through capillaries or tubes holds in the natural oak wood membrane as well. Table 3 shows that L_P decreases at all concentrations in the order :

Evaluation of f_{wm} and f_{sm} : On translating the thermodynamic coefficients into frictional coefficients, it has been found that L_P can be related to the coefficient of friction⁸ between water and the membrane, f_{wm} , by the equation :

$$L_P = \frac{\phi_w \bar{V}_w}{f_{wm} \delta} \quad \dots (5)$$

where ϕ_w is the volume fraction of water in the membrane, \bar{V}_w the molar volume of water at 35° and δ is the thickness of the membrane. ϕ_w has been determined by the method described by Ginzburg and Katchalsky⁹ using a vacuum oven for drying the wood. The value of ϕ_w in the present case came out as 0.177 ± 0.011 . By substituting the values for ϕ_w , \bar{V}_w , L_P and δ for the wood membrane of area of cross section 6.79 sq. cm. the values of f_{wm} for various solutions of KNO_3 , NH_4NO_3 , NaNO_3 and water have been estimated from the equation (5) and are recorded in Table 4.

TABLE 4 FRICTIONAL COEFFICIENTS, f_{wm} , AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF KNO_3 , NH_4NO_3 , NaNO_3 AND WATER AT 35°

Concentration $C(\text{Mol. l}^{-1})$	$f_{wm} \times 10^{-9}$ ($\text{dyn} \cdot \text{sec} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$)		
	KNO_3	NH_4NO_3	NaNO_3
0 (water)		0.59	
0.01	0.44	1.43	2.05
0.02	0.49	1.51	2.10
0.04	0.66	1.56	2.13
0.06	0.82	1.64	2.17
0.08	0.88	1.82	2.22
0.10	0.94	1.86	2.30

From the above table it is clear that frictional coefficient, f_{wm} , increases with the increase in concentration for a particular salt and has been found to be maximum in the case of NaNO_3 solutions.

The estimation of f_{sm} was carried out by using the following expression⁹ :

$$L_P = \frac{\phi_w}{\delta \left[\frac{f_{wm}}{\bar{V}_w} + f_{sm} (1 - \sigma) C_s \right]} \quad \dots (6)$$

where C_s is the concentration of the salt, σ the reflection coefficient and the other terms have their usual meanings. The expression (6) requires the evaluation of σ before attempting the estimation of f_{sm} . This has been described below.

If the hydrostatic pressure across the membrane is kept the same i.e., $\Delta P=0$ the equation (2) can be written as :

$$J_V = L_{Pd} RT \Delta C \quad \dots (7)$$

where R is the gas constant, T the absolute temperature and ΔC the concentration difference across the membrane. According to the above equation the plots of J_V versus ΔC at a particular temperature should be linear and it has been found to be so in the present case. The reflection coefficient data for the various solutions of KNO_3 , NH_4NO_3 and $NaNO_3$ at different concentrations is given in Table 5.

TABLE 5—REFLECTION COEFFICIENT DATA FOR THE VARIOUS SALT SOLUTIONS AT 35°

Concentration difference ΔC (Mol. l ⁻¹)	$J_V \times 10^8$ (cm ³ .sec ⁻¹)		
	KNO ₃	NH ₄ NO ₃	NaNO ₃
0.01	0.81	0.51	0.58
0.02	1.40	0.70	1.38
0.04	3.40	1.19	2.70
0.06	4.69	1.90	4.10
0.08	6.11	2.88	5.30
0.10	7.81	3.59	6.95

Using the value of $R=82.06$ cm³. atm. deg⁻¹. mol⁻¹ and $T=308^\circ K$ the value of L_{Pd} for KNO_3 , NH_4NO_3 and $NaNO_3$ has been found to be 3.47×10^{-8} , 1.44×10^{-8} and 2.64×10^{-8} cm³. sec⁻¹. atm⁻¹ respectively.

Staverman¹⁰ recognised that the ratio L_{Pd}/L_P is an adequate measure of membrane selectivity and he called it the reflection coefficient, σ . Using the value of $L_P=5.37 \times 10^{-2}$ cm³.sec⁻¹. atm⁻¹ the value of σ for KNO_3 , NH_4NO_3 and $NaNO_3$ have been calculated and recorded in Table 6.

TABLE 6—REFLECTION COEFFICIENTS OF VARIOUS SALTS THROUGH NATURAL OAK WOOD MEMBRANE AT 35°

Salt	$\sigma \times 10^3$
KNO ₃	0.59
NH ₄ NO ₃	0.27
NaNO ₃	0.49

From the Table 6, it is clear that the value of σ in each case is negligible and taken as equal to zero.

f_{sm} has been estimated from equation (6), using $\sigma=0$, and recorded in Table 7.

TABLE 7—FRICTIONAL COEFFICIENT, f_{sm} , FOR DIFFERENT SALTS AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS AND AT 35°

Concentration C (Mol. l ⁻¹)	$f_{sm} \times 10^{-4}$ (dyn.sec.cm ⁻¹ .mol ⁻¹)		
	KNO ₃	NH ₄ NO ₃	NaNO ₃
0.01	-0.82	-2.68	-3.88
0.02	-0.46	-1.41	-1.97
0.04	-0.31	-0.73	-0.99
0.06	-0.26	-0.51	-0.67
0.08	-0.21	-0.42	-0.52
0.10	-0.18	-0.35	-0.43

Table 7 shows that f_{sm} has got negative values suggesting that solute has negligible interaction with membrane. From the values of f_{wm} and f_{sm} for each salt it is clear that the values of f_{wm} are greater than those of f_{sm} suggesting that water has got more affinity towards solute than to membrane.

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